

The Church of the Theotokos of the Pharos

also known as “The Church of the Virgin of the Pharos”, “The Pharos Chapel”

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Entry tags: Constantinople, Christianity, Ritual Deposit, Christian, Religious Group, Byzantine, City, Religious Place, Monument, Shrine, Orthodoxy

The Church of the Theotokos of the Pharos was a chapel constructed in the eighth century in the midst of the Great Palace of Boukoleon in Constantinople (close to a lighthouse that gave the chapel its name) to house the instruments of Christ's Passion, which were soon joined by other celebrated items including the famous Mandylion of Edessa and numerous other relics. It is first attested in the entry of the Chronicle of Theophanes for the year 769 when it was the site of the wedding of Irene of Athens and Leo IV. After the end of Iconoclasm it was rededicated, an occasion which prompted Photios, who was patriarch at the time, to write a homily which offers us precious information regarding the church. In the intervening centuries, its collection of relics continued to grow, a fact attested by the itinerary of Anthony of Novgorod, as well as a list embedded in an account of the palace coup of John 'the Fat' Komnenos in 1200 authored by Nicholas Mesarites, who was skeuophylax of the church and was personally responsible for the care of its contents. During the sack of Constantinople during the Fourth Crusade, it avoided direct damage, and together with its contents was turned over into the care of the Latin Emperor Baldwin I. Nevertheless, the days of the Church of the Theotokos of the Pharos were numbered, and it presumably fell into disuse and ruin during the Latin occupation, as its contents were sold to fill the coffers of the beleaguered state. It is not attested in later sources. Relatively little can be ascertained regarding the form of the chapel save that it was small and extremely ornately decorated, features emphasized alike by Photios, Mesarites, Robert of Clari, and that it featured three apses, a central dome, and a narthex, suggesting that it, as restored in the 9th century, may have been an early example of the cross-in-square type. Moreover, given the Byzantine aesthetic predilection for intricate patterning and color, even the brief outlines which survive are suggestive to the historian's imagination, especially those that mention its impressive silver ciborium, its polychrome marble revetments, and the jewel-like opulence of its interior. Moreover, the appearance and especially the function of the chapel inspired that of La Sainte Chapelle (which would come to house much of the Pharos' former contents) as well as the Relic Chapel at Karlstejn.

Date Range: 760 CE - 1204 CE

Region: Constantinople, c800CE-1400CE

Region tags: Byzantium

Constantinople, c800CE-1400CE

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Michael Angold, 'The Coup of John the Fat' in *Nicholas Mesarites: His Life and Works* (Liverpool, 2017), 31-74.
- Source 2: Cyril Mango (ed.), *The Homilies of Photios, Patriarch of Constantinople* (Cambridge, 1958)
- Source 3: George Majeska, 'Russian Pilgrims in Constantinople', *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* vol. 56 (2002), 93-108.
- Source 1: Lidov, Alexei. "A Byzantine Jerusalem: The Imperial Pharos Chapel as the Holy Sepulchre." In *Jerusalem as Narrative Space* (Leiden/Boston: Brill, 2021)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://deremilitari.org/2014/01/robert-of-claris-account-of-the-fourth-crusade/>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: A lighthouse within the Great Palace of Constantinople

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

- Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The field is unsure of the date and circumstances of the foundation.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably Stone. Probably Wood.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Brick, Metalwork, Mosaic, Woodwork, etc.

Notes: Brick/Metal/Mosaic etc.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: We do not know much of the the specifics of its decoration beyond that it was extremely ornate.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: We do not know much of the the specifics of its decoration beyond that it was extremely ornate.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The interiors seem to have been furnished very lavishly as well.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely but there is no way to prove it one way or another.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably there were pervasive non-figural decorative elements.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no way of knowing this based on the information at hand.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: It is unlikely that statues were present given the typical Byzantine artistic idiom.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that reliefs were part of the decoration but it cannot be proven.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely they are present but there is no way to prove it one way or another.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely they are present but there is no way to prove it one way or another.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely they are present but there is no way to prove it one way or another.

Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Relics of the Passion arguably transfer the presence of God into the building.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: I do not know the specific properties attached to the site or to veneration of relics at the site in the capacity as intermediaries of communication with God.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no way of knowing this based on the information at hand, though presumably they did happen in some capacity.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: There is no way of knowing their details based on the information at hand.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: N/A

Notes: This cannot be ascertained with any certainty.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: N/A

Notes: Presumably the rituals in the Pharos took place according to well-established liturgical patterns.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Communion Wine.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably people who gained access to the site left ex votos or other tokens of veneration of

the relics contained within, but there is not direct proof of this.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: The existence of offices attached to the church implies that it was actively administered, which, in the Byzantine context, likely meant such prosaic matters as the maintenance of the fabric of the building were attended to at least for some periods.

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Though ostensibly a private chapel, various pilgrims apparently worshipped there.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: I do not know exactly how the Pharos was used as part of religious celebrations (as opposed to court ceremonial).

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Presumably yes due to the presence of relics

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time
– I don't know

↳ Present part time
– Yes

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - No

- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
 - Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: Offices are attached to the administration of the Church.

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably there was a sizeable endowment attached to the chapel but how exactly this was apportioned, what it consisted of, and what the fiscal-juridical status of the chapel was cannot be determined with any degree of certainty.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There may have been texts stored here, but we do not have any information regarding them.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Church of the Theotokos of the Pharos, Lidov, Alexei. "A Byzantine Jerusalem: The Imperial Pharos Chapel as the Holy Sepulchre". In *Jerusalem as Narrative Space*. Leiden; Boston: Brill, 2021.

Reference: The Church of the Theotokos of the Pharos, Klein, Holger. "Sacred Relics and Imperial Ceremonies at the Great Palace of Constantinople". In *Visualisierungen Von Herrschaft. Frühmittelalterliche Residenzen, Gestalt Und Zeremoniell*. Istanbul: German Archaeological Institute, 2006.